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Spatio-temporal monitoring of bankfull geometry using a semi-automated tool on high-resolution Digital Terrain Models

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Abstract— Understanding river channel bankfull geometry is essential for fluvial monitoring and flood forecasting. The bankfull stage represents the point where water begins to spill onto the floodplain, typically recurring every 1–2 years. This stage and its corresponding discharge play a pivotal role in shaping channel morphology, making it critical for river management and hazard assessment. In this study, we test *BankfullMapper*, a specialized MATLAB tool designed to detect river channel bankfull levels. The method divides the river into evenly spaced sections and extracts bankfull geometry by computing a hydraulic depth function for each section. This function plots elevation above the river thalweg against the area-to-width ratio, identifying points that correspond to the bankfull stage. Key indicators include: (i) the lowest breakpoints from the thalweg or (ii) the most prominent breakpoints. Additionally, Manning’s equation is applied to estimate bankfull discharge, enhancing the tool’s utility for hydrological analysis. We validate the approach using the Marecchia River as a test site demonstrating its capability to capture spatio-temporal dynamics of bankfull geometry and discharge. The semi-automated detection method delivers reliable, high accuracy (>0.8) results across diverse river types, showing optimal performance when using the lowest breakpoints from the thalweg. By focusing on morphological break identification, our approach provides a detailed and precise representation of bankfull geometry, making it a valuable asset for hydrological studies and river management.

I. INTRODUCTION

Detection of geomorphic features derived from Digital Terrain Models (DTMs) is critical for understanding the links between geo-hazards and human safety [1]. Improved availability and accuracy of digital topographic data allow detailed analysis of landforms and their connections to natural processes. Growing datasets highlight the need for tools linking geomorphometric measurements to geomorphological insights. These features serve as indicators of climate change impacts, aligning with the IPCC guidelines (2014, 2022) and the UN 2030 Agenda’s goal to adapt to climate change. Identifying this link is also a goal within the framework of Italy’s National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR), funded by Next Generation EU, extended partnership RETURN (multi-Risk sciEnce for resilientT commUnities under a changiNg climate) aimed to strengthen research on environmental, natural, and anthropogenic risks associated with climate change. In this regard, semi-automatic detection methods provide extensive data for large-scale analyses. River channel geometry and its relationship with floodplains offer insights into landscape evolution driven by climate, tectonics, and lithology [2]. In particular, bankfull stage, often linked to incipient flooding, is a key parameter for studying channel formation and flood hazards [3]. Bankfull discharge, with a recurrence interval of ~1.5 years, shapes channel morphology, which is increasingly affected by climate-induced shifts in precipitation patterns. Methods for

identifying bankfull geometry include: (i) qualitative field observations (e.g., floodplain breaks, inflection points), (ii) hydrological modeling using LiDAR data and software (HEC-RAS), and (iii) geometric terrain classification based on morphological breaks. Field methods, though accurate, are time-consuming and costly. Modeling requires advanced expertise, while terrain classification can be subjective. To address these limitations, we test the BankfullMapper tool [4], developed in MATLAB. It uses high-resolution DTMs to identify bankfull geometry and estimate discharge, focusing on semi-confined channels. Tested on the Marecchia River, it analyzes spatio-temporal dynamics of bankfull features, leveraging methodology by [5]. This tool integrates Manning’s equation for discharge estimation, offering a valuable resource for monitoring river systems and flood hazards.

II. MARECCHIA RIVER TEST SITE

The Marecchia River, stretching 70 km across northern Italy, drains 940 km² and flows into the Adriatic Sea. The study examines a 20 km segment affected by lithological heterogeneity and relevant anthropogenic modifications, including gravel mining and dam construction. Its humid subtropical climate (Cfa) averages 12.7 °C and 805.1 mm annual precipitation (1993–2022). Historical discharge records highlight several floods exceeding 200 m³/s, impacting sediment dynamics and channel morphology, particularly between 2009–2022.

Figure 1. Lithological map of the central Apennines of Italy together with the location of the Marecchia River catchment and the study river reach. The climate chart related to the Novafeltria locality for the period 1993 - 2022 is also reported. Reference system is WGS84.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

BankfullMapper [4] is a MATLAB-based tool built on the TopoToolbox v2 package [6], the workflow requires a DTM, an Height Above River (HAR) model, and river course as inputs. The test analysis performed on the Marecchia river course refers to the period 2008-2022. For 2008, the DTM derived from the LiDAR survey with density of points > 1.5 per m² (dataset available at [piano-straordinario-di-telerilevamento/\) was considered. This 2008-DTM has a ground resolution of 1 m and presents an error accuracy lower than ± 15 cm in elevation and ± 30 cm in plane and has been acquired between 2008-2009. For the 2022, the DTM derived from the LiDAR survey with density points > 4 per m² \(dataset available at <https://geoportale.regione.emilia-romagna.it/approfondimenti/prodotti-lidar-e-ortofoto>\) was considered. This 2022-DTM has a ground resolution of 0.5 m and presents an error accuracy lower than ± 8 cm in elevation and ± 30 cm in plane and has been collected between February and March 2022. For the analysis, the 2022 dataset was resampled to the resolution and extent of the 2008-2009 DTM.](http://www.pcn.minambiente.it/mattm/progetto-</p>
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The algorithm workflow is articulated in the following list of functions:

1. Transverse Section Definition (PROF Function): This step defines river cross-sections using the DTM, HAR, and river course data. HAR is derived through a three-step process: sampling river elevations, interpolating values, and detrending the DTM to produce relative elevation data. Optional inputs allow customization of section width, cross-section spacing, and smoothing.
2. Hydraulic Depth Function (BANKFULL Function): Hydraulic depth, defined as the area-to-width ratio, is computed at 10 cm increments from the thalweg to a user-defined elevation (e.g., 6 m). Peaks in the profile indicate potential bankfull stages.
3. Peak Detection (DETECT_PEAK Function): Peaks are extracted to identify breakpoints in channel morphology. Users can select all peaks, the lowest peaks (“lowest” mode), or the most prominent peaks (“max” mode). Kernel density estimates further refine probable values for elevation, area, and perimeter.
4. Discharge Estimation (MANNINGEQ Function): Manning’s equation estimates discharge based on hydraulic radius, slope, and roughness coefficients. This function is not currently tested in the present work. Slopes are calculated from section gradients or smoothed using TopoToolbox functions. Discharge values are computed for peak and probable elevations.
5. Mapping and Visualization (VISUAL Function): Bankfull elevation and discharge values are mapped for each section. Residuals between peak and probable values are also computed to highlight variations.

Bankfull extractions were then validated by comparing raster outputs with manually delineated active channel boundaries. Mappings considered low-flow channels, gravel bars, and sparse vegetation areas photointerpreted from orthophotos and prior study [7]. The model’s performance was evaluated using the

accuracy metric, calculated as the ratio of correctly classified pixels (true positives and true negatives) to the total number of pixels.

IV. RESULTS

The Marecchia River was analyzed for 405 sections in 2009 and 2022, using a 50 m step, 2500 m width, and 500 m planar smoothing (Figures 2 and 3). Results highlight differences in bankfull geometry and discharge over time. The "max" mode records higher elevations, with deviations between sections 255 and 350. The "lowest" mode in 2022 shows upstream elevation retreat, reflecting shifts from braided to wandering patterns.

Figure 2. Map view of the bankfull elevation change during the period 2009-2022 in "lowest" (a) and "max" (b) modes. Reference system is WGS84 UTM33N.

Width narrows from 200–800 m to 100–500 m, with flow areas following similar trends. Slope oscillates around 0.01 but exceeds 0.02 near the Ponte Santa Maria Maddalena check dam. Discharge calculations correlate with elevation changes, suggesting aggradation and degradation processes. Changes near Novafeltria and downstream highlight anthropogenic impacts, such as quarries, influencing peak elevation identification. Temporal comparisons reveal geomorphological changes over 13 years, impacting sediment transport and channel stability. Finally, model validation results showed that the "lowest" mode achieved an accuracy of 0.81, while the "max" mode performed slightly lower at 0.78. In 2022, the "lowest" mode improved to an accuracy of 0.83, with the "max" mode yielding a comparable value of 0.80.

V. DISCUSSIONS

A. Method Evaluation

The tool works well in semi-confined channels but struggles in V-shaped valleys or terraces with ambiguous breaks. Combining

modes offers complementary insights when validated by field data. The performance metrics suggest that the semi-automated detection method is generally effective, though its success varies with the selected mode and river course. Overall, both modes yield reliable results; however, the "lowest" mode consistently demonstrates higher accuracy, making it particularly well-suited for precise delineation of bankfull channels.

B. Interpretation and Limitations

The analysis of the Marecchia River reveals significant spatial and temporal variability driven by sedimentary processes and anthropogenic influences, underscoring the effectiveness of the method for dynamic river monitoring. Overall, bankfull elevation trends reflect a geomorphic transition from braided to single-thread and eventually to wandering reaches. From the river's headwaters to section 110, bankfull elevations range from approximately 1 m in the "lowest" mode to 2 m in the "max" mode. Between sections 110 and 255, the "lowest" mode shows a marked increase, approaching 2 m and aligning more closely with the "max" mode. In contrast, from sections 255 to 350—where the most pronounced temporal changes are observed—bankfull elevations in all modes decline to around 1 m.

Complementary flow area calculations, which are closely linked to changes in topographic elevation, reveal that sections 255 to 365 experienced notable elevation gains. This increase corresponds with a reduction in flow area over time, suggesting a proportional decrease in discharge. These patterns reflect both aggradation and degradation processes, as variations in bankfull elevation and discharge align with topographic shifts caused by sediment deposition.

The spatial and temporal heterogeneity of these changes highlights the complexity of the river system. Particularly notable shifts in bankfull elevation and discharge occur between Novafeltria and the Ponte Santa Maria Maddalena check dam. In this stretch, the "lowest" mode indicates a sharp decline in bankfull elevation between sections 255 and 320. Meanwhile, the "max" mode initially shows a slight increase near Novafeltria before following a similar downward trend. The pronounced drop in elevation near the check dam is likely influenced by anthropogenic structures, which may interfere with accurate detection of peak elevations in the "max" mode.

Despite its strengths in scalability and resolution, the method has limitations—particularly in areas modified by human activity, where misclassifications can occur. Additionally, its reliance on assumptions inherent in Manning's equation introduces uncertainty. As such, field validation remains essential to refine and support interpretations drawn from the analysis.

Figure 3. Plots along section number of the bankfull elevation (a), width (b), area (c), and channel slope (d). The average elevation changes for every section are also reported (e) (modified from [5]). “I” and “II” refer to the 2009 and 2022 respectively.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates the effectiveness of a semi-automated approach for extracting riverbank geometry, offering accurate, scalable, and adaptable insights into river morphology. The method’s use of morphological break identification enables a detailed and precise representation of bankfull geometry, as supported by performance metrics when compared to traditional mapping techniques. However, caution is warranted in areas with anthropogenic alterations or complex topography, where accuracy may be reduced. Future improvements—such as enhanced field validation and parameter optimization—hold promise for further increasing the method’s precision and broadening its applicability.

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